

ARAB NATIONALISM, A CASE STUDY OF BA'ATH PARTY IN IRAQ

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Abstract

There is no denying the fact that the Arab nationalism once was on its zenith during the mid 20th century, but it gradually began to fade away onwards and till 1990's, Arab nationalism had been replaced with the ethno-cultural or sectarian nationalism. True that the Ba'ath party had envisaged pioneering Arab nationalism when it laid the foundations of its movement in Syria and Iraq, it soon turned into an interest oriented party promoting the interests of Abd al Karim Qasimi and later on Saddam Hussein in Iraq and of Assad family in Syria. The internal and external policy maneuvers of these leaders at the platform of the given party in their respective countries left severe implications on Arab nationalism as a whole most of which being political and security related in nature. This article endeavors to explain the political as well as the security implications for the entire Middle East from the prism of the policies of the Baath party's of Syria and Iraq.

KEYWORDS: Arab, Nationalism, Baath party, ethno-cultural, implication.**INTRODUCTION**

There are two prominent variants. One variant view an Iraqi nation as involving Arab, Turkmen, Assyrian and Kurdish people as having a common Mesopotamian heritage; this view was promoted by Abd al-Karim Qasim, who was of mixed Arab-Kurdish descent. The second variant is a dual nationalism combining Iraqi nationalism alongside Arab nationalism, that supports Iraqi nationalism for matters involving Iraq and Arab nationalism for issues involving Arabs as a whole. Saddam Hussein believed that the recognition of the ancient Mesopotamian origins and heritage of Iraqi Arabs was complementary to supporting Arab nationalism. The Baathist regime officially included the historic Kurdish Iraqi Muslim leader Saladin as a patriotic symbol in Iraq; Saladin led Muslim and Arab forces during the Crusades. (Reich, 2005 Edition) Given the context of the Arab nationalism, many leaders and parties played their respective role in order to

materialize the long desired aspiration of the Arab Muslims throughout the Middle East to become one nation ideologically, if not geographically. Some of the key leaders who carried out the mission of the Arab nationalism are King Faisal I of Iraq, the great veteran leader of Egypt Jamal Abdul Nasser, the Libyan Leader Muammar Qaddafi, Yasir Arafat and Michel Aflaq.

However, the Baath leaders of Iraq and Syria who in the beginning did endeavor to bring the Arab world on a single platform, but soon deviated from their vision and began to promote their own manifested nationalism at the expense of the Arab nationalism. As a result, political differences led to uncertainty and the uncertain conditions led to the arms race. As fallout, the unity broke and a power struggle replaced Arab nationalism. Every country found itself superior to the other, especially when the personality cult of Saddam Hussein was being constructed, he was hailed not only the savior of the Muslims, but the greatest living Arab leader. These policies isolated the rest of the countries. (Isakhan, 2011)

The power struggle led to the creation of the communal differences within the countries and outside. The ethnic and religious minorities were marginalized and border and territorial disputes put the regional security at stake. For instance, Saddam brought the entire region of the Shatt al Arab in dispute. The invasion of Kuwait by Iraq also perturbed Saudi Arabia and other Gulf countries about their own security. As a result, they moved toward USA for help which finally gave USA and other Western powers to infiltrate their influence in the region striking a fatal blow to Middle Eastern nationalism and collective security. (Al-Kaysis, 2009)

Background of the growth of Baathist ideology in Syria and Iraq.

In the struggle against the Ottomans in the beginning and against the British in the later stages, the Arab Muslims launched the print media as the base for intellectual revolution and political awareness among the Muslim masses to understand their values and rights so that they cannot be exploited and manipulated at the hands of the British or any other external force with the ambition of aggrandizement and imperialist designs. The Ottomans had given those with massive scale of privileges who were supportive of their cause like the elite class.

The British followed the suit and established an oligarchic class of their own who had taken the advantage of alliance with the British and had controlled all the superior commissioned posts, all political posts and all important social positions leaving Muslims in the lurch with no help. This class was more inclined to serve the interests of the external

powers in return of the perks and favors given to them at the expense of the rest of the society who were victimized and subjected to inhuman treatment. Therefore, the creation of the Muslim print media was a great source of inspiration for the Muslims to emancipate them from all the miseries and troubles that had been inflicted upon them. (Said, 1993)

But soon it was quashed and subjected to the worst manner of censorship after the British had been thrown out of all the Middle East and the Ottoman Empire had been dismembered. The newly independent countries of Iraq and Syria had seen centuries of servitude and rule through monarchies and imperialists. Now the democratic set up was something quite new for them and most of them were not acquainted with the norms and values of democracy. As a result, before the democratic seeds could make roots within the society, monarchic rule assumed power within these two countries.

The Baathist parties which were gradually amalgamating power within these two countries found their way through the military establishment and toppled the monarchies respectively through coups. First Abd al Karim Qasim and later on Saddam in Iraq and Hafiz al Assad in Syria established the Baathist dictatorships in their respective countries. All these leaders mentioned above had their past affiliation with the military, therefore, the very first thing they did after assuming the control of the corridor of the power was to crush the independent thinking of the public and control and dictate their minds. (Seeberg, 2007)

For the very reason, the media was brought under direct state control; rather it was made the driving force behind the Baathist propaganda to promote their particular party interests. It started as a self-defense in the beginning, but after the independence it took a sweeping shift from its path and track. The post independence media was more controlled and less liberal in the early years of the freedom. The actual problem was in the fact that there were very limited rules and regulates to control and maintain the overall structure of print media when the country was suffering from other basic challenges for survival and stability when the coups took place in Syria and Iraq.

Beside controlling the media, they developed a personality cult in which the Baath leaders were shown as the saviors of the Muslims of Syria and Iraq and the minority chunks of population of Shia and Kurds and other communal groups who dared to raise their voice against these autocrats, were excommunicated from the mainstream process of development, thus, being denied of their share of the resources within the state. (Antonius, 2015)

Proliferation of mass weapons in the society

The public customs and mindset is a contributing factor in the demand of weapons and their preservation. Therefore, it can only be reduced through larger public awareness and public participation in every stage side by side with the government to make sure the proliferation of weapons is halted and the society moves toward prosperity and tranquility rather than violence.

Learning about one's own rights and duties is a turning factor since the people learning their duties will also learn about the rights of other and will do the least to violate them. Once they realize that the proliferation, use and preservation of weapons in the society as a custom harm the rights of the others, public will discourage all certain elements who propagate the weapons culture into the society. (Makiya, 1993)

Among those causes most of them were linked with the public behavior and public actions. Whether the weapons are legal or illegal, the public is partially responsible along with the government institutions for the massive scale of proliferation of small arms and light weapons.

When Egypt saw that Iraq was heavily investing in building its weapons industry, it followed the suit, the reason why Egypt was so curious about the military buildup of Iraq because these two countries were struggling for regional supremacy in the Middle East. Therefore, the weapons manufacturing of Iraq had a direct impact on Egypt. With the military focus of the Egypt, Saudi Arabia also followed the suit as the latter was not on good terms with the former since both of them were contenders for dominance of the Arab World. Hence, the arms race soon engulfed all the major Arab countries and a power struggle directly hampered the security stability of the region. (AbuKhalil, 1992)

Baathist as pawns in the great power politics using Arab nationalism for political interests

The origin of globalization can be traced back till the 16th century when west started to explore the new world. The East India Company was the first transnational company born. Emergence of financial institutions and trade organizations like World Bank, IMF, and GATT/WTO boosted the pace of globalization. Power politics of Cold War between the two super powers USA and USSR played a strong role in the process of globalization. Throughout the period Cold War, Iraq and Syria maintained their relations with USA and Soviet Union respectively serving the super power interests in the Middle East. (Ajami, 1991) Security is vital for any state because it is link to the survival of a state. Due to the impacts of globalization survival of nation state is in danger. Weaker and failed state have

more threats than the strong states. Agents of globalization like MNC'S, WB, IMF, WTO, NGO's and Non state actors like media are strong enough to influence the states like Syria and Iraq. These agents are playing across the borders of nation states independently through the tools of globalization.

Before the creation of United Nations there was no such kind of active NGOs in the world, but some voluntary organizations working around the world. NGOs (Non-government organizations) started functioning properly in whole world after the creation of United Nations. When imperial powers collapsed in the wake of World War 2 leading to decolonization, many states came into being in Asia, Africa, and Europe and in other regions. (Petras, 1999)

Whether it was Saddam Hussein or Anwar ul Saadat of Egypt or it was Muammar Qaddafi of Libya or it was the Assad family of Syria, all these people when assumed power, the first thing they sought was foreign help in order for legitimizing their power and strengthening their grip on the control of the state affairs. What could be expected from Saddam for regional integrity and peace of the region when he on the instigation of USA invaded Iran? This move was not hailed, but criticized throughout Middle East. The US instigation worked because it was using Iraq as a pawn to take vengeance against Iran for the Hostage Crisis of the 1979 that had culminated in the breakup of the diplomatic ties between the two permanently.

This move of Saddam claimed the lives of millions of people for no reason. Then, again being preoccupied with its aggrandizing ambitions, it invaded Kuwait in 1990. This time its own supporter USA launched the operation Desert Storm and destroyed the military capability of Iraq including its strategic infrastructure. The friend had betrayed Iraq and used it as a pawn. At the behest of the US instigation, Saddam not only wreaked havoc in the region, but also pushed Iraq to a war with USA; a war that it could never win. The results were devastating for which Iraq to this day is suffering and has not risen from the clutches of the chaos and devastation.

On the other hand, Syria was way too inclined toward USSR and after 1991 Russia. USA sought the Syrian-Iranian nexus as a growing threat to its regional interest and when both these countries began to move toward Russia, it had become obvious that USA was not pleased. The results were way too disastrous for Syria. Syria still is being victimized by the great power politics. As a matter of fact, this Syrian war has divided the entire Muslim world into two blocs; the pro-Assad bloc and the anti-Assad bloc. (Watts, 2014) An unabated civil war has engulfed the entire country; rather it has spilled over the other

parts of the region as well. On one side is USA who is supporting the rebels and the militants aligning with Saudi Arabia and the other Gulf countries and on the other side is Russia aligning with Iran and Hezbollah. The ultimate destruction is taking place in Syria tearing the country from its very foundations.

Militancy and terrorism have found new and stronger roots in the Middle East due to the weakening internal stability of the countries and this militancy is leaking to the neighborhood as well. Being a pawn in the great game of politics did not serve Iraq and Syria well, neither had it brought them any good nor did it bring the entire region of the Middle East any good. Arab nationalism had doomed to failure. (Hinnebusch, 2003).

Political impact of the Baath policies over the Arab world

History is witness that even in the ancient empires, there has been a role of general attitude of the public which has borne great resemblance to the empires and their security or the politics, still nonetheless, the word public opinion could not coin until the 18th century. In the ancient empires of Assyria, Babylonia and the Great Macedonian empires, public interaction with the ruler or the ruler's corresponding colleges has been witnessed. (Mill, 1988)

The Athens democracy is quite famous around the world just for the same practice of public relations and increasing public influence on the judgments and ruling of the crown. The words of Aristotle might add justification to the above-mentioned facts as he says that, "He who loses the support of the people is a king no longer."

But, Plato in contrast was opposed to the public ideas and public interaction with the ruling class as to him the public ideas distracted the ruling elite from their rationale, so, there must be a chosen and trained elite who must be assigned the task of promoting the ideas of the ruling class and they must be molding public attitude toward an affair and they must be guiding the ruling class to act upon a certain issue not the public. (Davison, 1958)

Arab nationalism, having lost almost everything, now has little to lose, and its endorsement of democracy and Islam has been made in just that spirit. That Arab nationalism should now cast itself as the defender of freedom and the faith is ironic. The irony is not lost on the Arabs themselves, who have a strong sense of history and long memories. They discarded Arab nationalism because it failed to keep its promise of power, even as it exacted an exorbitant price in freedom and faith.

It was not the only Utopian ideology to do so at the time. And perhaps the more useful comparison, when the perspective is longer, may be between Arab nationalism and Soviet communism: two great myths of solidarity, impossible in their scale, deeply flawed

in their implementation, which alternately stirred and whipped millions of people in a desperate pursuit of power through the middle of the twentieth century, before collapsing in exhaustion. In the garb of nationalism, every country served its own interests.

The Baathist rule in Syria and Iraq gave the other Arab leaders of Tunisia, Saudi Arabia, Yemen and Jordan the idea of totalitarian control and government. The idea of a utopian state was a mere dream for the public and it remains a dream to this day. The above mentioned leaders sought the idea of consolidating their rule over the masses through the totalitarian methods which they had learnt from Saddam and Assad family. They brought all the institutions, the media, the social sector under their direct control and controlled the means of production as well to ascertain that their rule lasted long. These totalitarian moves were specific for every country in a different method and did not bring the Arab world any closer, rather the rifts got wider. (Hinnebusch, 2003)

Nationalism for the ordinary people

The nationalistic approach has not been and is still not concretely useful and beneficial for the people in need for help. Baathist party workers had never been accountable to the local people but to overseas donors who review and oversee their performance according to their own criteria. The liberal class of the society believes that nationalism is actually part of the neo liberal agenda to roll back the state, open international borders for globalised commerce, deregulate labor markets to make hiring and firing easy and push all service provision into the hands of private sector. Third sector is hegemonic in itself. They dominate civil society to such an extent that even state seems much less powerful as compared to them. (Isakhan, 2011)

It further turns to the issue of accountability in providing international development assistance, and reveals a wide range of responses to these issues. They put democracy and human rights firmly at the centre of the debate about accountability far behind. Baathist ideology has not given the impression of true nationalism and liberty to the public at large, rather they have engaged in attempts to bring their own motives to flourish among the society and get engraved in the minds of the people. The local community was supporting the Baathist at the outset as they perceived them to work for social welfare of the society to the grass root level. (Bengio, 1998)

The Baathist working under government administrations and government started focusing on military power and their money used for government security purpose rather than social welfare of society. This was the purpose that allowed the Baathist to gain power and to enter the country, however, they have failed to deliver upon their agendas

and instead they are engaged in other types of activities like funding sectarian and terrorist networks, work as pressure groups and lobbies and to foment chaos. For an ordinary person, nationalism means nothing if the very basic needs and necessities for the very survival of that person are denied. Nothing comes before survival. (Dawisha, 2004)

Birth of communal and sectarian struggle; the reversal of Arab nationalism

The most heinous thing the Baath regimes in Syria and Iraq did was to sharpen the centuries old rivalries and animosities. Shia and Sunni have been living in the Middle East from the very outset of the religion of Islam and they have been at par with each other throughout different phases of history, especially, during the Umayyad and Abbasid periods. However, after that, centuries of silent and peace was witnessed until the Baath nationalism rekindled a new hatred among the different sects and communities.

The Middle Eastern region stretches over the sectarian fault-lines since the Arab world is divided into the Sunni majority states and the Shia majority states. What the Baath party factions of the above given two countries did in their attempt to consolidate their grip over the society, they created a privileged class of those who supported them or sympathized with them while a community of a deprived class also emerged which not only pushed them to the tight corner for their opposition to the autocratic rule, but also polished their centuries old animosities to the surface. (Bashkin, 2009)

Most of the people of the un-privileged class were from the Shia and Kurd communities in Iraq where a dominant Sunni was demonstrating despotism in the shape of Saddam. As far as Syria is concerned, there on the majority Sunni, a dominant Shia minority was ruling. These deprivations and the political alienation pushed them toward their ethnic, communal and sectarian hatred.

What remains more perturbing a fact is that these hateful practices got their way to the other countries in the neighborhood. As a result, the current scenario paints a very bleak picture of the sectarian and communal harmony in the Middle East, especially, after the Arab Spring. The problems have their roots in the rule of the Baathist regimes which have blown the very concept of the Arab nationalism away. (Dawisha, 2004)

Conclusion

To sum up, Arab Nationalism is an ideology of Arab Nationalists to work for the glory of Arab civilization, the language and literature of the Arabs and calling for rejuvenation and political unity of the Arab world. Arab Nationalism is a platform to unite the Arab world. To define, Patriotism is the belief which justifies the responsibility of a person to his country for further significant as compared to ones obligations to him or that of global

costs. Moreover, it is the aspiration to struggle Unfortunately, today it has doomed to failure almost its significance and various other to attain self government for your state or community.

The Arab patriotism can be name as a movement to bring together the Arabs including their culture, language, struggle from 1850-1939, but it took firm roots in twentieth century in Middle East principles literature and civilization. Although the Arab Nationalism has strong during Palestinian Independence dominate it in, the Middle East, while recently steps are under process to strengthen Arab Nationalism.

Historically speaking, the Ottoman Empire was dominating the Arabian Peninsula from sixteenth century. Then the young Turks revolted against the Ottoman Empire and strengthened the Arab Nationalism by providing equality and provincial Autonomy to the Arabs. The intervention of USA for help during the Gulf War finally gave USA and other Western powers to infiltrate their influence in the region striking a fatal blow to Middle Eastern nationalism and collective security.

The Arab countries got isolated from each other and they saw the internal chaos of each other with silence. The arms race soon engulfed all the major Arab countries and a power struggle directly hampered the security stability of the region. During the 1950's when the Arab world of more than 20 countries was being united a single platform began to divide in the late 1980's and early 1990's. Today, all the Middle East burns with internal chaos.

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